

Can Blockchain Prevent the Deterioration of Building Handover Information Quality for Higher Education Institutions?

Abstract

Purpose – This research investigates the distinct characteristics of blockchain technology to safeguard against the deterioration of handover information quality in the post-construction phase. The significance of effective management of handover information is highlighted by global building failures, such as the Grenfell Tower fire in London, UK. Despite existing technological interventions, there remains a paucity of understanding regarding the factors contributing to the decline in the quality of handover information during the post-construction phase.

Design/methodology/approach – This study employed a multi-case studies approach across five higher education institutions. It involved conducting semi-structured interviews with 52 asset management professionals, uncovering the underlying reasons for the decline in handover information quality. Building on these insights, the study performed a mapping exercise to align these identified factors with blockchain technology features and information quality dimensions, aiming to evaluate blockchain's potential in managing quality handover information.

Findings – The study findings suggest that blockchain technology offers advantages but has limitations in addressing all the identified quality issues of managing handover information. Due to the lack of an automated process and file-based information exchange, updating handover information still requires an error-prone manual process, leading to potential information loss. Additionally, no solutions are available for encoding drawings for updates and validation.

Originality/value – This study proposes a framework integrating blockchain to enhance the information management process and improve handover information quality.

KEYWORDS: Handover Information, Information Quality, Asset Information Management, Blockchain Technology, Higher Education Institutions

26 **1 Introduction**

27 Inadequate information can introduce significant organisational inefficiencies, culminating in major financial
28 challenges. Batini and Scannapieco (2016) highlight the severe financial repercussions of poor information
29 quality. They point to the 2002 Data Warehousing Institute report, which revealed that US businesses suffered
30 an annual loss exceeding \$600 billion due to inferior information quality (Eckerson, 2002). Similarly, the
31 Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry is not immune to these losses. Matarneh *et al.*
32 (2019) highlighted that poor asset information management in the post-construction phase leads to an
33 estimated annual loss of \$10 billion in the US building industry. Moreover, recent building failures linked to
34 insufficient handover information management pose financial risks and further compromise the safety of
35 occupants (Hackitt, 2017).

36 Handover information (HO) is the primary asset information source for the management of buildings
37 (Pinheiro, 2019). Initially static, this information evolves dynamically in response to change throughout the
38 building's lifecycle, requiring an effective information management solution (Leygonie, 2020). Investigations
39 into various building failures have exposed the detrimental consequences of pervasive deficiencies in current
40 building information management practices, leading to inaccurate, incomplete, and outdated information,
41 which poses serious safety consequences (Hackitt, 2018; UK, 2022). Building Information Modelling (BIM)
42 holds the potential to augment handover information quality. However, its application is predominately in
43 new construction, which constitutes about only 1 to 2 per cent of the total building stock annually (Roberts *et*
44 *al.*, 2018). Consequently, BIM's information management capacity often bypasses pre-digital era
45 constructions reliant on legacy information, which lacks transparency and accountability, especially in the
46 verification of updates by stakeholders. With approximately 85% of the buildings in the European Union
47 predating BIM, the importance of effective information management is significantly heightened (European
48 Commission, 2020). This situation illuminates the urgency of addressing existing shortcomings in practices,
49 particularly emphasising the vital importance of trustworthy handover information.

50 Blockchain technology, recognised for its potential to uphold the quality of handover information, offers a
51 promising avenue for streamlining information exchange across various disciplines in a building project

52 (Nawari and Ravindran, 2019). Blockchain is a decentralised ledger that records and shares every transaction
53 within the network among its participants (Mukherjee and Pradhan, 2021). Blockchain has the potential to
54 address prevalent issues in handover processes, such as insufficient record-keeping, inadequate paperwork
55 furnished by contractors, and challenges in accessing information (Ali *et al.*, 2020). Its capacity to provide
56 audit trails illuminates transparency and accountability (Mahmudnia *et al.*, 2022). Blockchain's transparency
57 ensures a clear understanding of the ledger's status, enhancing participant accountability, while its traceability
58 feature allows for the verification of information with accurate timestamps (Kshetri, 2017; Montecchi *et al.*,
59 2019). Offering a secure, uniform, and transparent approach, blockchain stands out as a suitable alternative to
60 traditional centralised systems, improving the quality of the information (Love *et al.*, 2005).

61 Evaluating the features of blockchain in this context uncovers opportunities for innovation and improvement
62 in information management within the higher education sector, posing the following research question:

63 ***How can blockchain technology help prevent the deterioration of handover information quality for higher***
64 ***education institutions during the post-construction phase?***

65 This study adopts a multi-case study approach, investigating higher education institutions across the UK,
66 Ireland, Germany, and Northern Ireland. Motivated by prior research underscoring asset management
67 inefficiencies due to subpar asset information quality in these institutions, it aims to devise information
68 management strategies from their diverse building types, applicable to commercial buildings (Curvelo
69 Magdaniel *et al.*, 2019; Syafar *et al.*, 2020). Semi-structured interviews with asset management professionals
70 yielded nuanced insights into their perspective, completed by onsite observations for validations. A
71 significant focus was a mapping exercise to explore blockchain's potential in addressing the fundamental
72 causes of information quality decline. This study distinguishes itself from previous blockchain research by
73 initially identifying specific evidence-based causes of information deterioration and then examining the
74 suitability of blockchain for improvements. Its objective is to develop an empirically grounded solution to
75 prevent the deterioration of handover information quality, particularly focusing on overcoming asset
76 management challenges in the higher education sector.

77 This research is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on handover information in building
78 management, information quality dimensions and characteristics of blockchain technology. Section 3 outlines
79 the methodology for evaluating the potential of blockchain to prevent information quality decline. Section 4
80 proposes a blockchain information management framework, addressing the identified information
81 deterioration causes. Section 5 discusses a critical analysis of the findings. Section 6 offers theoretical and
82 practical contributions, discusses the research limitations, and suggests future research directions.

83 **2 Literature review**

84 This section discusses the relevant studies on the role of handover information in building asset management,
85 the characteristics of information, and the features of blockchain technology. The literature review includes
86 academic journals, conference papers, industry publications, and standards. This study follows the Data,
87 Information, Knowledge and Wisdom (DIKW) hierarchy, positing that information is data that has been
88 processed, organised, and contextualised (Frické, 2009).

89 2.1 The role of building handover information in building asset management

90 Upon completion of a building project, a comprehensive set of handover information is handed one-off to the
91 asset owner, serving as the main data source about the project (Fang *et al.*, 2022; Pinheiro, 2019). This
92 handover includes three information types: graphical, non-graphical, and project-related documentation (BSI,
93 2013). Graphical information generally encompasses as-built drawings and 3-dimensional models supported
94 by the Building Information Modelling (BIM) (Chang *et al.*, 2022; Fang *et al.*, 2022). Non-graphical and
95 documentation offer supplementary details, including operation & maintenance (O&M) manuals, product
96 information, warranty certificates and testing reports, contributing to a holistic perspective of the building
97 project (Cavka *et al.*, 2015; Chang *et al.*, 2022; Kassem *et al.*, 2015). The asset owners commonly dictate
98 specific information requirements (BSI, 2013). Accordingly, contractors involved with a building project
99 provide the required information during the handover phase (Zhu *et al.*, 2021).

100 Handover information is crucial for managing complex-built physical assets such as buildings, guiding regular
101 maintenance and operational support to ensure the functionality and longevity of buildings (Chang *et al.*,

102 2022; Pinheiro, 2019). According to ISO 55000, this information is essential for a strategic, coordinated
103 approach to managing multiple assets (Fang *et al.*, 2022; Petchrompo and Parlikad, 2019). This information
104 also significantly impacts building energy simulations, improving energy efficiency and achieving sustainable
105 development goals (Pinheiro, 2019). However, despite its importance, there is limited understanding of why
106 the quality of handover information deteriorates.

107 2.2 The definition of information, its characteristics and information quality dimensions

108 The effective management of handover information demands understanding its nature, management
109 perspective and quality standards. Information is processed data, can be repurposed without losing value yet
110 may become outdated (Batini and Scannapieco, 2016; Mingers, 1996). Information management involves
111 creating, acquiring, organising, storing, disseminating, and using information. Correspondingly, Wang *et al.*
112 (1998) advise treating information like a manufactured product: recognising the specific needs of the
113 information, managing the information as a product, overseeing the information throughout its lifecycle, and
114 appointing dedicated roles to administer information. Concepts from manufacturing quality management can
115 assess required quality attributes (Borek, 2012).

116 Quality information is commonly defined as information satisfying user requirements, categorised into four
117 types (English, 1999; Wang and Strong, 1996). Wang and Strong (1996) proposed four categories of
118 information quality: intrinsic, contextual, representational and accessibility data quality. Intrinsic quality
119 focuses on accuracy and credibility, while contextual quality emphasises relevance and timeliness.
120 Representational quality deals with ease of understanding, and accessibility quality concerns secure and easy
121 access. English (1999) further classified the characteristics of dimensions into two broad categories: (1)
122 Inherent information quality and (2) Pragmatic information quality. Inherent quality refers to data that can
123 stand alone, such as ‘accuracy’ and ‘non-duplication’. Pragmatic quality focuses on meeting end-user needs,
124 including ‘accessibility’ and ‘usability’.

125 Combining the English and Wang and Strong’s approaches, the Data Management (DAMA) UK Working
126 Group published six core quality dimensions, including the definitions and the related characteristics: (1)
127 Completeness, (2) Uniqueness, (3) Timeliness, (4) Validity, (5) Accuracy, and (6) Consistency (UK DAMA,

128 2013). Therefore, this study adopts the DAMA’s six primary quality dimensions to analyse the preferred
129 quality characteristics of handover information:

- 130 • Completeness: All required data are present to meet the user's requirements
- 131 • Uniqueness: No data is recorded more than once
- 132 • Timeliness: All required data are sufficiently updated for the task
- 133 • Validity: All data conform to the syntax (e.g., format, type, etc.) within its definition
- 134 • Accuracy: Data correctly represent the actual value
- 135 • Consistency: The absence of difference when comparing two or more data sets

136 2.3 Blockchain for handover information management

137 With the expansion of quality principles into the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry,
138 blockchain technology has emerged as a noteworthy candidate for the management of information quality.
139 Blockchain and other forms of distributed ledger technologies (DLT) are databases of transactions hosted in a
140 distributed network without a need for a central administrator (Perera *et al.*, 2020). A chain of blocks called
141 the blockchain is created by grouping transactions into blocks, each containing a hash to the preceding block
142 (Mukherjee and Pradhan, 2021). For a succinct overview, **Table I** summarises the salient features of
143 blockchain relevant to information management, complemented by practical examples and implications.

144 Blockchain technology offers high transparency, traceability, and version control, serving as a reliable
145 historical record-keeping system (Li and Kassem, 2021). Its core feature, distributed ledger technology (DLT)
146 provides a single reliable source of information for all stakeholders by storing identical records across nodes
147 to enhance the credibility of the information (Hijazi *et al.*, 2021). The decentralised nature of blockchain
148 eliminates single points of failure, improving resilience and data integrity (Perera *et al.*, 2020). It also
149 facilitates better data exchange, contributing to sustainability by ensuring transparent material and data origins
150 (Shojaei *et al.*, 2019). Blockchain-based Material and Product Passports provide a trustworthy information
151 source throughout the whole lifecycle of a built asset (Li and Wang, 2021). Security is another strong suit:
152 data manipulation is nearly impossible as changes must be made across all nodes and blocks(Mukherjee and

153 Pradhan, 2021). The technology employs consensus mechanisms and public-key cryptography to maintain
154 data integrity and privacy (Perera et al., 2020). One of the most fundamental features is smart contracts, self-
155 executing codes that operate without intermediaries once set conditions are fulfilled (Mukherjee and Pradhan,
156 2021). These contracts foster trust among stakeholders (Kim *et al.*, 2020). However, there have yet to be
157 validation studies that confirm the acclaimed benefits of blockchain technology in managing asset
158 information, including handover information (Wang *et al.* 2017).

159 **Table I Principles of blockchain.**

160

161 2.4 Applications of blockchain in the AEC industry

162 Several studies showcase the applications of blockchain's versatility, particularly its problem-solving
163 capabilities rooted in payment systems, collaboration and documentation, throughout various stages of a
164 building's lifecycle (Li and Kassem, 2021; Mahmudnia *et al.*, 2022). In the design phase, the blockchain's
165 immutable record-keeping feature tracks all design changes, streamlining the design collaborative
166 coordination process to minimise ambiguities in design documents (Di Giuda *et al.*, 2020). Moreover,
167 blockchain applications extend to improving supply chain management and progress payments in construction
168 to avoid construction delays (Ahmadisheykhsarmast and Sonmez, 2020; Qian and Papadonikolaki, 2020).
169 Beyond construction, Götz *et al.* (2020) advocate leveraging blockchain for documenting post-construction
170 operational data and information, ensuring the preservation of essential information for future use and
171 complying with the legal duties of operating buildings (Li *et al.*, 2019).

172 2.5 The gap of knowledge in quality handover information management

173 The review of the literature reveals a knowledge gap in using blockchain technology for managing building
174 handover information. Three main issues exist. Firstly, there is a dearth of discussion on integrating dynamic
175 information characteristics with blockchain technology to manage trustworthy handover information.
176 Secondly, the potential of blockchain technology is often highlighted without empirical evidence, particularly
177 in the AEC industry, that illustrates its practical use or detailed analyses. Lastly, the relationship between
178 specific quality concerns in handover information and the limitations of blockchain-based handover

179 information management remains unexplored. Consequently, a new study is needed to assess the feasibility of
180 blockchain in addressing the identified quality concerns, offering a fresh outlook on the issue of "rich"
181 information but "poor" quality.

182 **3 Methodology**

183 This research adopted a multi-case strategy to assess the feasibility of blockchain in preventing handover
184 information quality corrosion. Following Yin's (2018) recommendation, this research leveraged a case study
185 approach for real-life insights, with comparative analysis enhancing the robustness of findings. This study
186 combined semi-structured interviews and direct site observations to corroborate the participants' input. The
187 investigation progressed in three phases: a narrative literature review identified frameworks and
188 methodologies related to handover information management, information quality management in the AEC
189 industry, and blockchain for managing construction-related information. Next, five case studies with higher
190 education institutions explored the causes of the quality deterioration in handover information in the post-
191 construction phase. The final phase evaluated the potential of blockchain in addressing the identified causes.

192 3.1. Case Selection

193 This study adopted a case-based approach for in-depth investigations in a real-world context, ideal for small
194 sample sizes (Patton, 1999; Saunders *et al.*, 2019). The study strategically focuses on the higher education
195 sector to derive information management strategies from its varied building functions, which can be
196 applicable to a wide range of commercial buildings. Guided by Miles *et al.* (2018), this study developed the
197 following selection criteria:

- 198 1. Type of sector: higher education institutions,
- 199 2. Type of physical assets: portfolios of buildings of various ages and different uses,
- 200 3. Type of process: the use of handover information to support asset management processes.

201 The appropriate number of cases for multi-case study research is a debated topic. Nonetheless, this study
202 followed the widely accepted principle of theoretical saturation for determining the optimal number of cases,

203 as suggested by Eisenhardt (1989). This study selected cases from various countries to avoid contextual
204 biases. Chosen organisations use globally recognised technological tools for managing handover information
205 and adopt the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) 55000 standards to manage their physical
206 assets. Profiles of the selected cases are detailed in Table II.

207 **Table II Summary of the selected cases.**

208 3.2 Data Collection and Analysis

209 This study involved conducting semi-structured interviews with participants from each case, primarily aimed
210 at gaining a comprehensive understanding of the following aspects:

- 211 1. Organisational structure: Defining the roles and responsibilities within the Estates Division.
- 212 2. Process: Streaming the flow of handover information pertaining to various projects.
- 213 3. Utilisation: The use of handover information and its quality requirements.
- 214 4. Management: The use of asset information management systems.

215 Table III lists 52 participants from five cases, all regular users of handover information in their job duties.
216 Each interview spanned between 60 and 90 minutes. With the consent of the participants, interviews were
217 recorded and transcribed to ensure accuracy and transparency. Participants received interview transcripts for
218 review and verification, enhancing the study's reliability.

219 **Table III Participant profiles.**

220 This research adopts an inductive approach. NVivo, a qualitative data analysis software, analysed interview
221 data to understand the handover information quality decline (Miles *et al.*, 2018). After thematic analysis, the
222 Root Cause Analysis (RCA) technique pinpointed the root causes of quality corrosion. A comprehensive
223 cross-case analysis provided further insights. These causes were then compared with blockchain technology
224 characteristics to assess its potential in addressing these issues, leading to the proposition of a blockchain-
225 based framework, utilising smart contracts for updating and validating handover information.

226 **4 Findings**

227 4.1 The Results of Comparative Analysis

228 This section provides six root causes of the handover information quality deterioration across five cases,
229 determined through thematic analysis: (1) irregular handover information management, (2) evolving
230 technology leading to heterogeneous formats, (3) information loss, (4) exogenous factors, (5) human errors,
231 and (6) leadership impacts. Figure 1 was also created based on the occurrences of the reported issues from
232 each case. The purpose of this figure is not to make statistical inferences but to compare the reported problems
233 visually.

234 4.1.1 Irregular Handover Information Management

235 The findings across cases consistently demonstrate that irregular management processes for handover
236 information affect the quality of the handover information, as stressed by Woodall *et al.* (2013). Each case
237 identified two primary sources of handover information: major (e.g., new projects, extensive renovations) and
238 minor projects (e.g., equipment replacement). Despite the sources of handover information, *'the information
239 management process is a bit fluid'* and *'separate information is sitting all over the place in a central
240 information management system'* without understanding the intended use of the information (C1_P1 and
241 C1_P20). As a result, *'it is a challenge to get 'accurate' and 'up-to-date information* (C1_P1, C1_P2 and
242 C1_P19). Moreover, C4_P1 argues that a lack of information flow of *'lots of minor works and projects across
243 the campus becomes problematic'*. Supplementally, *'the issue here in terms of handover documentation is to
244 do with multiple small projects'* without understanding the roles and responsibilities of managing such
245 information (C1_P20). In aligning this view, C2_P4 and C4_P4 confirm that *'we need to have 'robust
246 procedures'* for handling handover information for minor projects.

Figure 1 Comparative analysis of case studies.

4.1.2 Evolving Technology leading to Heterogeneous Formats for As-Built Drawings

All cases manage buildings of diverse ages, and most buildings predate the AutoCAD era. As a result, each case manages as-built drawings in different formats, which have been predominately influenced by evolving technological advancements in the AEC industry (Love *et al.*, 2018). The recent adoption of BIM has introduced additional non-conventional formats, particularly for drawings such as 3-dimensional models and IFC files. Consequently, ‘we have varieties of as-built formats, including hard copies, mylars and blueprints, AutoCAD files, and Revit models’ (C3_P4). In earlier days, the ‘physical drawings were scanned without considering the risk of altering the original scale of the drawings’, but the modified scaled drawings are solely intended for schematic viewing (C1_P18, C4_P2 & C5_P1). Dissimilar formats frequently require ‘conversion’ to useful formats (C1_P1). The quality consequences of using as-built drawings in multiple formats are presented in the following section.

4.1.3 Information Loss

The analysis indicates that information loss is twofold. As previously mentioned, diverse formats of drawings contribute to information loss, especially when converting the existing formats to useful formats. For example, ‘when we transfer the drawings from CAD files to a PDF format, then obviously we lose some of the detail

264 *and richness behind the CAD plans*' (C2_P1). Similarly, *'when we convert 3D models into 2D plans, we lose*
265 *the richness of information embedded in the 3D models. At the same time, we lose some information when*
266 *converting from 2D plans to 3D models*' (C4_P2).

267 Another contributing factor to information loss is the gradual erosion of the vital handover information, as
268 Yilmaz *et al.* (2015) pinpointed. Physical documents are susceptible to *'misplacement'*, *'damage'*, and
269 *'deterioration'*, further exacerbating critical information erosion over time (C1_P9, C3_P4 & C5_P2). For
270 example, older buildings tend to have less comprehensive information than newer construction. C2_P6 added,
271 *'we have fewer than 10 sheets of drawings for the 200-year-old structure, while the BIM-based projects*
272 *provide an unparalleled volume of handover information'*. This disparity is attributed to *'outdated*
273 *documentation practices'* and *'insufficient record-keeping systems'* prevalent during earlier times (C4_P9 &
274 C5_P6). Further, the mismanagement of handover information is compounded by *'the absence of*
275 *standardised procedures'* for managing such information and the inadequate implementation of information
276 migration strategies when adopting new technological solutions (C1_P18).

277 4.1.4 External Factors

278 Continuous updates in building regulations and relevant requirements often give rise to confusion and
279 inconsistencies when gathering essential handover information. This, in turn, leads to incomplete information
280 and the possibility of errors (C1_P25, C2_P3, C2_P7, C4_P4 & C4_P9). For instance, the fire, life, and safety
281 systems have progressively advanced over the years (C2_P3 & C4_P8). These evolving updates create a
282 situation where asset owners lack a comprehensive understanding of the information and adequate
283 information, which hampers the quality of the handed-over information. Furthermore, the intricate nature of
284 compliance measures and reporting obligations can pose challenges in compiling accurate and complete
285 information (C1_P25). These complexities can overshadow meticulous documentation practices, resulting in a
286 decline in the quality of the handover information (C1_P26, C4_P4 & C5_P3).

287 While effective documentation practices are instrumental in improving the quality of handover information,
288 the existing AEC industry has yet to develop dedicated digital tools for managing legacy handover
289 information (C1_P11, C1_P15 & C1_P18). Many buildings predating the AutoCAD era continue to rely on

290 numerous physical files, outdated formats, and disorganised records for their management. These physical
291 documents are prone to misplacement, damage, or even destruction, directly impacting the information's
292 quality. Concurrently, legacy information collides with digitally formatted handover information (C2_P4,
293 C3_P4 & C5_P6). As a partial solution, a platform-based approach is commonly adopted for storing and
294 exchanging file-based information, but this solution requires converting physical documents into usable
295 formats (C4_P7). As mentioned earlier, the integrity of documents can be altered during the conversion
296 process, limiting the future use of information.

297 4.1.5 *Human Errors*

298 Handover information may suffer from negative impacts due to human errors and mistakes, even those that
299 seem minor or insignificant (C1_P1, C2_P1 & C4_P1). One commonly reported error was the improper
300 distribution of handed-over information to incorrect asset information management systems or information
301 depositories. This mistake often results in the loss of valuable information as the intended information ends up
302 in the wrong location (C1_P1, C1_P21 & C3_P3). Recurring mistakes were observed in incorrectly tagging
303 equipment and components (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2015). This led to inaccurate labelling and categorisation of items,
304 causing additional resources and time-consuming processes for verification, particularly for insurance
305 inspections. Moreover, the data entry errors in the asset information system had significant consequences. For
306 instance, incorrectly naming a building or using the wrong address resulted in information loss, inefficiencies
307 in retrieving information, and potential safety risks for occupants in emergencies.

308 4.1.6 *Leadership Impacts*

309 The absence of leadership support hinders the quality of handover information. This is mainly due to leaders
310 not understanding the role of handover information in the post-construction phase. Their failure to see its
311 importance makes it hard to allocate resources and implement effective strategies to improve the management
312 approach, ultimately affecting the quality. The lack of leadership support is a major obstacle to achieving
313 high-quality handover information. Without garnering support from leaders, the value and use of this
314 information are often overlooked, leading to mismanagement (Masood *et al.*, 2016). This misunderstanding
315 negatively impacts the efficiency after construction. Educating leaders about the crucial role of handover

316 information can ensure smooth post-construction operations, as indicated by all cases (C1_P20, C2_P15,
317 C4_P4, C7_P2 & C7_P3).

318 The comparative analysis identified six underlying reasons behind the quality decline in handover
319 information, notably irregular information management processes and information loss. Additionally, the
320 quality of as-built drawings was evaluated in light of technological advancement, while human errors and lack
321 of leadership support contributed to the quality deterioration. However, the quality effects caused by external
322 factors remain unexplored in current research. In the following section, the identified root causes are mapped
323 against the characteristics of blockchain technology to explore the potential of blockchain in addressing
324 quality dilemmas.

325 4.2 Mapping of blockchain characteristics to root causes

326 Figure 2 illustrates the mapping of quality issues, blockchain features and the six core information quality
327 dimensions identified in the literature (UK DAMA, 2013). The mapping exercise aims to illustrate the
328 possibilities of addressing quality issues (as shown in the outer circle) correlates with the characteristics of
329 blockchain, which are represented in the middle circle of the diagram. The cross-analysis of the case study
330 revealed that inconsistent handover information management during the post-construction phase hugely
331 affects the quality of handover information. This specific cause was mapped to the corresponding blockchain
332 features identified in the literature: ‘single source of truth’, ‘transparency’, ‘traceability’, and
333 ‘decentralisation’. For example, defining roles and responsibilities for managing handover information can be
334 enhanced by well-defined smart contracts, increasing the transparency of stakeholders’ tasks and activities.
335 All submitted documents will be recorded in an immutable manner, enabling to trace the information as long
336 as the blockchain exists. Moreover, the decentralised concept of managing documents removes one
337 controlling party revising the documents. Combining these attributes will achieve a ‘single source of truth’ for
338 asset information to support the future use of buildings.

339 Subsequently, the blockchain features are connected to the relevant information quality attributes of
340 information quality in the handover information, which is displayed in the central circle of the figure. For
341 example, completeness of information would be ensured by providing a blockchain-based historical record of

342 all transactions and by incorporating smart contracts to detect incomplete information. Blockchain ensures
343 uniqueness as it provides a single source of truth for all participating nodes. Keeping track of all versions of
344 the files and their metadata provides data timeliness, accuracy, and validity, which is strengthened even more
345 by the immutability of blockchain records. The consistency of data records is ensured by smart contracts
346 validating if the information is classified correctly.

347 In the mapping exercise, leadership impact was not mapped to any characteristics of blockchain. The
348 leadership impact caused by the quality deterioration of handover information is not an isolated cause, but
349 support from leadership is necessary to realise the full benefits of implementing blockchain technology to
350 prevent the quality decline. Features like ‘anonymity’ and ‘protection of IP rights’ were also not mapped
351 because these features are irrelevant to the handover information management. This exercise culminated in a
352 proposed conceptual framework for managing handover information irrespective of project size as the asset
353 owners update different assets.

Figure 2. Mapping of root causes, blockchain attributes and data quality dimensions.

4.3 Framework proposal

Leveraging blockchain’s benefits, a conceptual framework is proposed for gathering handover information using blockchain and smart contracts (Figure 3). The process begins with the client defining handover information requirements, which are then encoded into a smart contract. This contract validates the completeness of information uploaded by the contractor. Once the construction phase concludes, the contractor submits the handover information to the selected cloud platform designated by the client. A smart

362 contract, communicating with the Application Programming Interface (API), records transaction metadata on
 363 the blockchain and checks the information against the encoded requirements. If any information is missing,
 364 smart contract will notify the contractor to re-upload the necessary information. After the smart contract
 365 confirms the completeness of the submitted information, it forwards the submitted documents to the architect
 366 for review. Once approved, the final documents are submitted to the client. This general framework facilitates
 367 both major and minor projects during the post-construction phase of a built asset.

368

369 Figure 3. A conceptual blockchain framework of handover information collection process.

370

371 Furthermore, the example illustrates the use of blockchain and smart contracts in streamlining the update of
 372 handover information in a minor project. In the scenario, a contractor replaces a boiler and consequently
 373 updates the product specification and warranty documents in the cloud-sharing platform selected by the client.
 374 The metadata of the updated information is recorded on the blockchain by the smart contract, which also
 375 updates the information in the product passport. For graphical information, such as 2D drawings or 3D
 376 models, current technology does not allow encoding the validation of drawings as part of the smart contract,

377 which limits updating in the product passport. Therefore, the client will observe that the drawings or 3D
378 models related to the replacement units are missing from the product passport review.

379 **5 Discussion**

380 The investigation into handover information management reveals that robust information management is
381 pivotal to maintaining the integrity and quality of information. These findings align with Masood *et al.*
382 (2016), who underscores the critical role of uniform information management processes in ensuring the long-
383 term quality of information. Further compounding these issues, Yilmaz *et al.* (2015) pinpoint the tangible
384 risks associated with physical information loss and the adverse effects of outdated and ineffective record-
385 keeping methods on the quality of handover information.

386 Transitioning to the broader context, information is constantly evolving through major and minor projects,
387 ranging from extensive renovations to equipment replacements. Each project represents a transactional update
388 event, where accuracy is critical to prevent cascading issues. Love *et al.* (2018) stress the importance of
389 precision in maintaining as-built drawings. Despite the critical nature of managing transactional updates, the
390 task of updating graphical information and corresponding non-graphical information remains vulnerable,
391 mainly due to its reliance on manual updates. This vulnerability stems from the ingrained nature of asset
392 information management in current workflows. Further, there is a notable knowledge gap concerning the
393 effects of poor legacy information management and the assimilation of evolving regulatory demands on the
394 quality of information. This indicates underlying systemic issues in information governance, extending
395 beyond technological solutions.

396 Viewed through this transactional lens, blockchain emerges as a potential, though not originally developed as
397 an information management tool. Blockchain addresses specific concerns, such as immutability and
398 decentralisation, which are highly relevant to asset information management. While blockchain cannot create
399 new information or rectify digitalisation errors, it offers a reliable mechanism for tracking the provenance and
400 changes made to asset information. over time, this could lead to the creation of more reliable information.
401 Furthermore, blockchain's immutable nature ensures that every transaction is recorded with the necessary

402 quality for managing the long lifespan of buildings. The adoption of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)
403 like blockchain could markedly improve the efficiency in the detailed documentation and tracking of updates
404 with foundational trust in business relationships, especially in the AEC industry (Qian and Papdonikolaki,
405 2020).

406 It is noteworthy to state that blockchain's security feature is significant, yet this study indicates asset
407 management professionals, especially in higher education, may underemphasise security concerns. Parn and
408 Edwards (2019) stressed the need to harness blockchain's security for protecting assets in high-risk
409 environments, such as banks, prisons, and defence facilities. Although resilient, blockchain is not impervious
410 to threats. Yli-Huumo *et al.* (2016) raised a cautionary note about vulnerabilities, such as the '51% attack',
411 where control over half of the network could lead to blockchain manipulation. This risk illuminates the
412 necessity for vigilant management and robust strategies when implementing blockchain technology.

413 In sum, it is critical to weigh blockchain's benefits against its limitations and consider its function in an
414 extensive operational context. Key aspects include fostering trust and developing an integrated strategy to
415 handle assets' amassed digital and physical information. Utilising blockchain to enhance transactional and
416 provenance tracking in asset management can significantly improve information quality.

417 **6 Conclusions**

418 This research's evidence-based case study approach identified the root causes of handover information quality
419 deterioration based on multiple cases. A blockchain-based framework was then proposed to improve the
420 management of handover information, aligning the identified root causes with blockchain features and
421 information quality dimensions. This approach, not presented in previous studies, highlights the unique
422 challenges and limitations of implementing blockchain technology in the management of asset information,
423 including building handover information.

424 This study offers theoretical and practical contributions. On a theoretical level, it positions blockchain
425 technology as a potentially disruptive innovation yet acknowledges its limitations in fully addressing the

426 complexities of handover information management. It challenges the assumption that blockchain can entirely
427 overhaul existing information flows and associated processes in the cases studied.

428 Practically, the study provides managers and practitioners with a framework to improve the quality of the
429 handover information management process using blockchain technology. The study highlights the need for
430 organisations to tailor blockchain solutions to their specific needs, ensuring effective enhancement of the
431 information quality. The research underscores the importance of bespoke strategies in integrating blockchain
432 technology to prevent quality deterioration in handover information, illuminating the practical implications.

433 Building on vital insights from asset management professionals, this study proposes a conceptual framework
434 for managing handover information. However, this study poses certain limitations. Its scope is narrowly
435 confined to information management in asset management, excluding a facilities management perspective. A
436 notable challenge identified is the extensive outsourcing of facilities management tasks in the participating
437 organisations, a trend noted by Adhikari *et al.* (2019). Consequently, future research is essential to evaluate
438 blockchain's productivity and cost-benefits for developing a refined prototype or proof of concept. Such
439 research is crucial for a broader scale, including by third-party service contractors accessing and updating
440 asset information.

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